

What Innovation-Thinking, Blockchain/Cryptocurrencies, and more can help us achieve!

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

The Sustainable Development Goals are humanity's greatest challenges and I believe that it's going to require a combination of systems-thinking, exponential-thinking, and design-thinking mindset to achieve those goals in a more efficient, expedient, and effective manner. Altogether I call this "Innovation-Thinking" and let's use this mindset to approach problem-solving in a "kill multiple birds with 1 stone" format; in short – this mindset is all about social innovation.

2. Aim

We're going to look at a combination of some of those SDGs (of-or-related to the environment and sustainability, the future of work, and the future of the way we'll be living) and apply innovation-thinking to see how things like blockchain, circular design, and suburbia fit together amongst others

3. Material and methods

A video will be shown describing the SDGs, then a brief introduction about why I'm focusing the talk on those 3 above areas – sustainability, future of work, and future of living. This will be followed up with an infographic describing what "innovation-thinking" is, which will then be proceeded by a discussion of methods we can apply. Methods will be a combination of systemsthinking tools such as "interconnectedness", "synthesis", "emergence", "feedback loops", "causality", "systems mapping", design-thinking tools such as most notably "circular design", and exponential-thinking tools such as a personal invention – a chart that describes the relationship between business viability and technological viability in conjunction with how they fit in withregards-to their timing. This chart will take into consideration of the "hype cycle". Other tools and methods may also be employed for this talk.

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4. Results

The startup I'm currently conducting research for which will be built to tackle this problem. I essentially aim to prepare us for a smarter, more efficient, and sustainable way of living, working, and relating to our environment in the future. This is inspired in part by this.

5. Conclusions

How can we get there from today but all the while – by staying lean and agile? The answer will be presented at the end

6. Key Words

Design-Thinking, Exponential-Thinking, Systems-Thinking, Lean, Agile, Hype, Blockchain, Cryptocurrencies, Circular Design, Suburbia